

Current and future measurements of electron neutrinos and electron antineutrinos in the T2K off-axis near detector

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1. The T2K experiment

Long-baseline neutrino oscillation experiment.

- Baseline = 295 km, Beam peak energy = 0.6 GeV
- Optimised to measure θ_{13} through **electron neutrino appearance** in a muon neutrino beam.

→ Differences between ν_e and ν_μ cross sections is of increasing importance to the future of neutrino oscillation experiments.

2. The near detector

ND280 is situated 280 m downstream of the source.

In T2K electron neutrino appearance analyses, ν_e from oscillation are the signal, while ν_e intrinsic to the beam form the largest background.

ND280 measures:

- ν_e component of the beam [1]
- ν_e cross-sections [2]

Two fine-grained plastic scintillator detectors (FGD) provide the target mass.

These are enclosed by detectors designed to track particles:

- Time projection chambers (TPC) and Electromagnetic calorimeters (ECAL)
- These subdetectors are enclosed by a magnet operating at 0.2 T.

3. Selecting ν_e CC and $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC interactions

We search for ν_e CC and $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC events in both ν -beam and $\bar{\nu}$ -beam mode.

However, due to the currently low statistics of $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC in $\bar{\nu}$ -beam mode, we do not present this here or use it for a cross section at present.

- Apply **data quality checks**, and require beam **timing** compatibility.
- Select the **highest momentum negative track** that originates in the **FGD** fiducial volume (FV) and makes a track in the **TPC**.

ν -beam: ν_e CC after track selection

- Particle identification (PID): **TPC PID** (dE/dx) on the selected track. In suitable cases, include additional **ECAL PID** (charge distribution).

ν -beam: ν_e CC after PID

$\bar{\nu}$ -beam: $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC after PID

- Additional cuts for $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC selection to remove **proton background**
 - Look for positrons showering in FGD2
 - Perform FGD PID for tracks that stop in FGD2
 - Additional ECAL PID to separate hadronic interactions from EM showers
 - Cut on: ECAL EM Energy / TPC momentum
- Reject pair production** ($\gamma \rightarrow e^+e^-$) events by looking for a positron, and cutting on the invariant mass.
- Veto upstream activity** to reject background outside of FGD1.

ν -beam: ν_e CC
Purity: 0.54, Efficiency: 0.29

$\bar{\nu}$ -beam $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC
Purity: 0.54, Efficiency: 0.31

We also select $\bar{\nu}$ -beam ν_e CC with
Purity: 0.47,
Efficiency: 0.32

4. Distinguishing ν_e CC0 π interactions

A ν_e CC0 π event is defined such that there are no pions in the final state.

- Cut on the number of **additional tracks** while aiming to **allow for protons**.
 - No more than one FGD-only track
 - Maximum of one FGD-TPC tracks, and only if it has p -like and non π -like TPC PID
- Reject events with **delayed FGD activity** that indicates the presence of a **pion that has decayed** into a muon and subsequently to a Michel electron.

ν_e CC0 π with a proton ejected into a TPC.

ν -beam: ν_e CC0 π
Purity: 0.47 Efficiency: 0.32

5. ν_e CC-other control sample

A ν_e CC-other interaction is defined as any ν_e CC that is not ν_e CC0 π .

The sample is selected from the events that pass the ν_e CC cuts and satisfy one or more of the following

- FGD activity indicating pion decay
- ≥ 2 additional FGD-TPC tracks, or ≥ 2 FGD-only tracks.
- 1 additional FGD-TPC track that is π -like and non- p -like, in the presence of 0-1 FGD-only tracks

6. γ -background control sample

γ -event: e originates from FGD1 FV but comes from a photon

Large uncertainties on these types of events due to

- π^0 production
- ν vertex outside of FGD1: mass uncertainty, interactions on heavy elements

γ -sample in ν -beam

- Pass ν_e CC PID selection
 - Fail pair production cut (i.e. γ -like)
 - Pass upstream vetoes
- 90% pure in γ -events

7. Systematics

The ν_e CC, $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC and ν_e CC0 π selections have similar systematic uncertainties.

Below is a breakdown of the systematic uncertainties for the signal and γ -background in the ν -beam ν_e CC selection.

8. Current and Future work

A log-likelihood method for extracting the ν_e CC, $\bar{\nu}_e$ CC and ν_e CC0 π cross sections has been developed. The ν_e CC measurement will utilise both ν -beam and $\bar{\nu}$ -beam data in a simultaneous fit.

Number of protons on target used here: ν -beam: 5.8×10^{20} , $\bar{\nu}$ -beam: 6.3×10^{20} . Including the more recent data taking periods, these statistics will nearly double.

References

- [1] Abe, K. *et al.* (T2K collaboration), Phys. Rev. D 89, 092003 (2014)
- [2] Abe, K. *et al.* (T2K collaboration), Phys. Rev. Lett. 113, 241803 (2014)